

VAAC Model Setup Tables

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Introduction

A global network of nine Volcanic Ash Advisory Centres (VAACs) are responsible for monitoring and producing forecasts of volcanic ash clouds to assist the aviation community in planning their operations and minimising risk. To generate their forecasts the VAACs make use of observations of the eruption and resulting ash cloud, numerical weather prediction data, and dispersion modelling.

Forecasts currently consist of a Volcanic Ash Graphic (VAG) and associated text description, referred to as the Volcanic Ash Advisory (VAA), which convey the expected location of the ash cloud up to 18 hours ahead. Since November 2020, the International Civil Aviation Organisation (ICAO) has requested that this information is also provided in digital format. In recent times the aviation community has also requested, in an ad-hoc manner, that the VAACs or their supporting organisations provide longer-range forecasts out to T+24, T+36 and further ahead. In Europe, following the eruption of Eyjafjallajökull in 2010, the national meteorological centres hosting the London and Toulouse VAACs also provide supplementary concentration charts which indicate how much ash is expected to reside in the atmosphere.

Forecasting naturally requires the use of numerical models. All VAACs use highly complex atmospheric transport and dispersion models to provide the basis of the forecast guidance that they issue. This document outlines the current operational model setups used by the VAACs. It should be noted that this document is simply intended to represent a snapshot in time of the configurations used. Therefore, this should not be used as a guide to actual model capability, as operational demands i.e., lack of reliable information, speed, etc dictate that certain functionality not be used.

For clarity the model set-ups are presented in a series of tables. It is recognised that this format may limit the scope to explain more complex aspects. To present this information in such a concise form then 'default' or 'typical' settings may be all that is described. Where practical, note has been made of more 'advanced' operational user options. For a fuller description the reader is directed to the references contained in this report and the wider literature and documentation that is available.

These tables were first compiled as part of the VAAC Best Practice process for the VAAC 'Inputs and Outputs' Modelling Workshop held at NCEP, Washington in November 2012 and are now part of regular update cycle.

- Version 1 (Nov 2012) of this 'Snapshot' document was part of the full Workshop report.
- Version 2 (March 2016) compiled for the VAAC Best Practice Workshop, held at the National Meteorological Service (SMN) in Buenos Aires, Argentina, 2016.
- Version 3 (Nov 2018) compiled for the VAAC Best Practice Workshop, held at the National Weather Service (SMN), Wellington, New Zealand, 2018.

Category 1: Source Characterization

This table describes the application of key source terms, often referred to as Eruption Source Parameters (ESPs), used to initialise the atmospheric transport and dispersion models.

Source Characterization	Anchorage & Washington	Buenos Aires	Darwin	London	Montréal	Tokyo	Toulouse	Wellington
Horizontal location at source	Smithsonian Institution. Can be varied.	Smithsonian Institution. Can be varied.	Smithsonian Institution. Can be varied.	Smithsonian Institution. Can be varied.	Smithsonian Institution. Can be varied.	Smithsonian Institution. Can be varied.	A list of active volcanoes in Toulouse VAAC AoR with SI data. Can be varied.	Smithsonian Institution. Can be varied.
Horizontal dimensions/ geometry at source	dx, dy = 0	$\Delta x = \Delta y = 0.25$ deg big domain $\Delta x = \Delta y = 0.15$ deg small domain	variable, based on Zidikheri and Lucas (2020)	dx, dy=0	Default radius of 1000m. May be edited.	Radius = $Kr * z$ $Kr = 0.198$, z:height	$\Delta x = \Delta y = 0.5$ deg (Global domain) or 0.1 deg (Nested grid with ARPEGE) or 0.125 deg (Nested grid with IFS) 4 x 4 grid cells used with Gaussian horizontal distribution	Point source

Source Characterization	Anchorage & Washington	Buenos Aires	Darwin	London	Montréal	Tokyo	Toulouse	Wellington
Bottom of source	Height of the vent taken from Smithsonian Institution	Height of the vent taken from Smithsonian Institution. May be edited.	Height of the vent from Smithsonian Institution. May be edited	Height of the vent taken from Smithsonian Institution. May be edited, bottom set to observed plume base or set from buoyant plume output	Height of the vent taken from Smithsonian Institution. May be edited.	Summit Elevation / observed plume base	Height of vent/summit. May be edited.	Height of the vent taken from Smithsonian Institution.
Top of source	Input by analyst based on observations	Based on observations.	Input from VAAC staff. Generally based on observations.	Based on observations	Based on observations.	Based on observations	Based on observation	1. Based on observations if any (user entered and/or VOLCAT) 2.S/M/L defaults from Mastin et al 2009 USGS report
Vertical distribution	Uniform	Suzuki Distribution	Variable. Based on Zidikheri & Lucas (2020), depends on height of eruption	Uniform by default	Uniform by default but possible to choose other fixed distributions (umbrella, exponential etc.)	Suzuki Distribution	Uniform or Umbrella	Uniform
Mass Eruption Rate (MER)	Run with unit mass. Area of discernable ash shown by using relation similar to Mastin 2009 to	MER from Woodhouse et al., (2013)	MER from Zidikheri & Lucas (2020)	Fraction of MER (kg/s) from Mastin et al. (2009) or Buoyant plume model (Devenish,	MER in $\mu\text{g}/\text{h}$ from Sparks 1997 or Mastin 2009. May be edited.	$\text{MER}=\text{K}*\text{H}^{4.0}$ $\text{K}=193\text{kg}/\text{km}^4$	MER from Mastin (g/hr) (default) Can be changed according to forecaster's decision.	Mastin et al 2009 (S/M/L) or user input

Source Characterization	Anchorage & Washington	Buenos Aires	Darwin	London	Montréal	Tokyo	Toulouse	Wellington
	determine threshold. Can be adjusted by analyst to get a bigger/smaller area.			2016) or can be set manually.				
Eruption Duration	Input by analyst	Start time based on ground/satellite observations, continuous release or pulse depending on volcano	Variable. Input by analyst, but 24 hours default.	Based on observations, assume continuous release but can represent pauses	6 hours by default. May be edited.	Ongoing eruption: during forecast period VA away from volcano: none	Based on observation.	Start time based on user input or observations (VOLCAT). Also, Mastin et al 2009 for S/M/L scenarios
Fine Ash Fraction	Adjustable	Variable according to PSD following Mastin et al., 2009	Variable, based on Zidikheri & Lucas (2020)	Default 5% MER, for PSD 0.1 – 100 µm. Can be varied	10% MER	~ 18 % of total mass, for < 100 µm (Log-normal PSD. Suzuki, 1983)	5%	5%
Multiple Eruption phases	Yes	Yes	Generally no operationally	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Near Source Physics Schemes Available	No	No	No	Buoyant Plume (Devenish, 2016)	No	No	No	No
Data Fusion Methods for ESPs Available	No	No	Ensemble filtering based on observations, either VOLCAT retrievals or VAAC polygons	Inversion	No	Data insertion	No	No

Category 2: Species Properties

This table describes the physical properties assigned to pollutant represented in the modelling.

Species Properties	Anchorage and Washington	Buenos Aires	Darwin	London	Montréal	Tokyo	Toulouse	Wellington
Particulate (P) or Gas (G)	P	P	Either, P is default	P	P	P	P	P
Single size (S), Particle Size Distribution (PSD) See Appendix for PSDs	PSD	PSD	PSD, 4 options depending on volcano	PSD Variable	S, PSD	PSD	PSD* or S (Can be changed according to forecaster's decision)	PSD
PSD range, diameter (μm)	0.6 - 20	0.06 - 62.5	0.2 - 100	0.1 – 100/125	Several options	10-100:plume 1-10:VA cloud (can be varied)	0.1 - 62.5	0.65 - 65
Number of bins	4 discrete	11 bins (with cut-off)	25 bins, with 11 between 10 and 30 μm	Continuous Variable bin number, Default 6	Several options	Continuous	6 if PSD	5
Density (kg m^{-3})	2500	1000 - 2600	2500	2300	2500	1000-2400 (dependent on particle size)	2300	2500
Non-Sphericity	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No

Category 3: NWP Data Used

This table describes the forecast meteorological data, taken from Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) models, used to drive the atmospheric transport and dispersion models.

Met Data	Anchorage & Washington	Buenos Aires	Darwin	London	Montréal	Tokyo	Toulouse	Wellington
NWP data source name	GFS, GEFS, NAM	GFS	ACCESS (ensemble+det), GFS, ECMWF (det only)	Met UM (Default): Global (Deterministic), Ensemble (MOGREPs-G) ECMWF HRES	GDPS (Global), RDPS (Regional), HRDPS (High resolution)	JMA-GSM (MSM, LFM)	ARPEGE, IFS	GFS, IFS, WRF
Ensemble Met Data	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No
Number of Ensemble Members	31	N/A	36	18	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Temporal resolution used (hours)	3:3:1	1	1	3	1	3	3	3/3/1
Horizontal resolution (Lon, Lat)	GFS 0.25 degree; GFS and GEFS 0.5 degree; NAM 2.5 km over Hawaii, 12 km Alaska, 3 km CONUS	0.25 deg (big domain) and 0.15 deg (small domain)	ACCESS GE3: 0.3-0.45 deg lat-lon ACCESS G: 0.12x0.18 deg lat-lon	Global Deterministic: 0.141°x 0.094° (~10 km at 50°N) MOGREPs-G 0.281°x 0.188° (~20 km at 50°N) ECMWF HRES 0.25°x0.25° (~25 km at 50°N)	15; 10; 2.5 km	0.25x0.25 deg	(0.5,0.5) deg (Global domain) (0.1, 0.1) deg (Nested grid with ARPEGE) (0.125, 0.125) deg (Nested grid with IFS)	GFS: 0.25 deg IFS: 0.125 deg WRF: 4 km

Met Data	Anchorage & Washington	Buenos Aires	Darwin	London	Montréal	Tokyo	Toulouse	Wellington
Horizontal extent (Global, Regional)	G; G; R	G	ACCESS – global GFS – global EC - regional	G	G; R; R	G	G (with optional nested grid)	GFS: Global IFS: Regional WRF: Regional
Vertical levels used	56; 23;40	41	70 (ACCESS, not all relevant)	59	62	21	28 (ARPEGE); 20 (IFS)	GFS: 27 IFS: 11 WRF: 51
Max altitude	13hPa; 20hPa; 19 hPa	10 hPa (~30 km)	Nominally up to 260,000 ft with ACCESS	30 km Above 30 km a persisted met approach is used	31 km	10 hPa (~30 km)	10 hPa (~30 km)	GFS: 7 hPa IFS: 100 hPa WRF: 50 hPa
NWP forecast length (hours)	84h; 84h; 48h	48	96 h (+96 h before valid time)	144	240; 84; 84	264 (00, 12UTC) 132 (06,18 UTC)	84 or 180	GFS: 60 h IFS: 60 h WRF: 84 h
Update frequency (hours)	6	6	6	12 Deterministic 6 MOGREPS-G	12; 6; 6	6	12	GFS: 3 h IFS: 3 h WRF: 1 h

Category 5: Dispersion Model Outputs

This table describes the datasets output from the model runs and options used for graphics generated from these datasets.

Outputs	Anchorage & Washington	Buenos Aires	Darwin	London	Montréal	Tokyo	Toulouse	Wellington
Output Resolution	0.1 degree for 24h, 0.25 deg for 24-48h)	0.25 deg (big domain) or 0.15 deg (small domain)	0.2 deg default, but settable	0.25 deg	1 to 50 km	0.5 deg (can be varied)	(0.5,0.5) deg (Global domain) (0.1, 0.1) deg (Nested grid with ARPEGE) (0.125, 0.125) deg (Nested grid with IFS)	0.1 deg
Vertical layers	3 layers. SFC-FL200, FL200-FL350, FL350-FL550	FL050 to FL600 every FL050 (12 levels)	7 layers, but four changeable settings for low, medium, tropopause or stratospheric	FL050 to FL600 every FL050 (12 levels)	SFC-FL200, FL200-350, FL350-600, SFC-FL600; 7x2 km layers from SFC-14km	FL000-180, 180-550 (can be varied)	15 pressure levels + FL000-200, 200-350, 350-550	11 layers, from SFC to FL500 each 5000 ft.
Exact FL	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No (Grid level approximation)	No
Quantity	Discernable	g/m3, g/m2	g/m2, mg/m3	g/m3, g/m2, base, top, age	g/m3	kg/m2(for operation), kg/m3, base, top	g/m3, g/m2	g/m3, g/m2, base, top
Standard plotting projections	Depends on volcano latitude	Lat/Lon	Lat/Lon	Lat/Lon cylindrical	Orthographic, Polar stereo, Lat/Lon-cylindrical	Lat/Lon	Lat/Lon	Lat/Lon
Standard forecast length (hours)	48	24	24, but variable	120	72	18	84-180 for global domain	24 h

Outputs	Anchorage & Washington	Buenos Aires	Darwin	London	Montréal	Tokyo	Toulouse	Wellington
							24 from launch of the simulation with nested grid.	
Time interval	1(for 24 h), 6&12 for 48h	1	3 h default (variable)	3 h	1 (variable)	1	6 (1 hourly for first 36h)	3 h
Time Average (hours)	1 ending at valid time.	0 (Eulerian Model)	Instantaneous. Snapshots at valid times	1 ending at valid time	1 ending at valid time (same as output interval)	No; Snapshot at valid time	0 (Eulerian Model)	1 ending at valid time
Standard model update frequency (re-run of disp. model)	6h (variable)	6 hourly or as necessary	On demand	6 hourly	6 hourly	6 Hourly	6 Hourly (variable)	6 hourly

Category 6: Computational Details

This table describes the computational platforms used and associated details.

Computational Setup	Anchorage & Washington	Buenos Aires	Darwin	London	Montréal	Tokyo	Toulouse	Wellington
Run time	~5 minutes	13 min (big domain) 3 min (small domain)	~10 min standard, longer with more options (up to 60 min)	5 min, 30 min (same for Ensemble)	7.5 min	2.5 min	~30min approx.	5-30 min (running 9-member ensemble)
Forecast length (hours)	48	24	24	24, 120	72	18	84-180 for global domain 24 from launch of the simulation with nested grid.	24
Platform	x86 Linux	x86 Linux	BoM supercomputer (Cray XC40)	UKMO HPC (Cray XC40) x86 Linux	Cray's CS500, Linux workstations (Ubuntu)	x86 Linux	x86 Linux	Linux
Parallel	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Cores	8	24	up to 100	128	40	480	128	1
Run Time for 24 hours (estimate from above)	1 minute	13 min (big domain) 3 min (small domain)	10 min	5 mins	2.5 min	3.3 min	10 min. 20 min with nested grid	5 min

Computational Setup	Anchorage & Washington	Buenos Aires	Darwin	London	Montréal	Tokyo	Toulouse	Wellington
Core time (run time * cores)	8	312		640	100	1600	1280	5

Category 7: Data Fusion and Intervention Methods

This table describes any data fusion methods used directly with the atmospheric transport and dispersion models, it also summarizes any observations that VAAC operational meteorologists may use to set the source terms, analyse forecasts, and manually intervene on the model output.

Data Fusion	Anchorage & Washington	Buenos Aires	Darwin	London	Montréal	Tokyo	Toulouse	Wellington
Data Fusion and Intervention Methods	No	No	Ensemble filtering	Inversion	No	Data insertion	No	No
Satellite Observation Data Used	All, GOES, Himawari,	GOES, TERRA, AQUA, Suomi NPP	Himawari, others if available	All (MSG-SEVIRI, Himawari9-AHI, GOES18+16-ABI, AQUA-MODIS, TERRA-MODIS, Suomi-NPP VIIRS, NOAA-20/21 VIIRS, Metop-A,B,C-IASI and AVHRR)	GOES, Himawari, METEOSAT	Himawari, Metop, Suomi	-	Himawari
Satellite Retrieval Data Used	VOLCAT (not directly ingested into model but utilized by analyst.) Pavalonis et al. (2015a,b)	Ash RGB, BTM, ash height, VOLCAT	VOLCAT (if available)	Utilized by analyst: Dust RGB, Detection confidence, mass loading, effective radius, ash cloud height. Used in inversion: Mass loadings (g/m ²)	VOLCAT (ash height) RAMMB-SLIDER (BTM), NASA SPoRT (ash RGB), Satellite feed from antennae	Satellite imagery (location, ash SSheight)	-	VOLCAT (ash height)

Data Fusion	Anchorage & Washington	Buenos Aires	Darwin	London	Montréal	Tokyo	Toulouse	Wellington
Ground Observation Data Used	Webcams, VONA, social media,	Webcams, VONA and Reports, SYNOP, METAR/SPECI	Webcam, VONA, Social media	UK Lidar + Ceilometer network, VONA incl Radar and webcam obs	Webcams, seismographs, VONA, weather stations	Webcams, VONA	-	N
Airborne Observation Data Used	soundings	PIREP	PIREP, soundings	PIREPs	PIREPS, Soundings	PIREPS	-	N
Outputs		Manual input		Manually adjusted polygons. Inversion: updated set of source emissions	Manual input	Manual input	-	N

Appendix: Particle Size Distributions

Buenos Aires VAAC

Standard, Cordón Caulle, 2011. Adapted from Bonadonna et al. (2015).

Diameter (μm)	Mass fraction (%)	Cumulative mass fraction (%)	Cut-off (True/False)
0.06	0.0	0.0	
0.1	0.0	0.0	T
0.2	0.0	0.0	T
0.5	0.1	0.1	T
1.0	0.3	0.4	T
2.0	0.9	1.4	T
3.9	2.0	3.4	T
7.8	3.1	6.5	T
15.6	3.4	9.9	T
31.3	2.7	12.6	T
62.5	1.7	14.3	T
125	1.1	15.4	F
250	1.6	17.0	F
500	3.7	20.6	F
1000	7.4	28.0	F
2000	11.9	39.9	F
4000	15.3	55.2	F
8000	15.8	71.1	F
16000	13.1	84.1	F

32000	8.6	92.7	F
64000	4.5	97.2	F
128000	1.9	99.1	F
256000	0.9	100.0	F

Coarse, Ruapehu, 1996. Adapted from Bonadonna, C., Houghton, B. F., (2005).

Diameter (μm)	Mass fraction (%)	Cumulative mass fraction (%)	Cut-off (True/False)
0.06	0.0	0.0	T
0.1	0.0	0.0	T
0.2	0.0	0.0	T
0.5	0.0	0.0	T
1.0	0.0	0.0	T
2.0	0.0	0.0	T
3.9	0.04	0.04	T
7.8	0.2	0.2	T
15.6	0.6	0.8	T
31.3	1.6	2.4	T
62.5	3.8	6.2	F
125	7.4	13.6	F
250	11.9	25.5	F
500	15.8	41.3	F
1000	17.4	58.7	F
2000	15.8	74.5	F
4000	11.9	86.4	F
8000	7.4	93.8	F
16000	3.8	97.6	F
32000	1.6	99.2	F
64000	0.6	99.8	F
128000	0.2	99.9	F
256000	0.1	100.0	F

Fine, Hudson 1991. Adapted from Scasso et. al., (1994).

Diameter (μm)	Mass fraction (%)	Cumulative mass fraction (%)	Cut-off (True/False)
0.061	0.00	0.00	T
0.122	0.00	0.00	T
0.244	0.00	0.00	T
0.488	0.00	0.00	T
0.977	0.00	0.00	T
1.953	0.13	0.14	T
3.906	2.25	2.39	T
7.812	12.07	14.46	T
15.625	21.14	35.60	T
31.25	13.14	48.75	T
62.5	9.05	57.80	T
125	17.20	75.00	F
250	17.07	92.07	F
500	6.80	98.86	F
1000	1.07	99.93	F
2000	0.07	100.00	F
4000	0.00	100.00	F
8000	0.00	100.00	F
16000	0.00	100.00	F
32000	0.00	100.00	F
64000	0.00	100.00	F
128000	0.00	100.00	F
256000	0.00	100.00	F

VAAC Darwin

Each volcano in the VAAC Darwin region has been assigned a default PSD, based on a survey conducted by Adele Bear-Crozier. This is a changeable option to one of the others on demand by the forecaster. PSD_1 is based on Rose et al (2007) with a Mafic composition for eruption types M0, M1, M2 and M3. PSD_2 is based on Hobbs et al (1991) and is for Silicic eruption types S0 and S2. PSD_3 is based on Bear-Crozier et al (2012) and is for Silicic eruptions type S1. PSD_4 is based on Durant et al (2009) and is for Silicic eruption type S3.

The large number of size bins are included to capture the subtle effects of differential fall speeds from different size particles. Work suggested that the regions between 10 and 30 mm are where the fastest rate of change in the fall speed occurs, so we have maximized the number of bins there to better capture this sensitivity.

Diameter (mm)	PSD_1 emission rate	PSD_2	PSD_3	PSD_4
0.2	0	0.001	0.001	0
0.65	0.005	0.005	0.0316	0.015
2	0.009	0.05	0.0213	0.0775
6.5	0.095	0.2	0.0524	0.09
10	0.02936	0.06364	0.02909	0.04795
12	0.02936	0.06364	0.02909	0.04795
14	0.02936	0.06364	0.02909	0.04795
16	0.02936	0.06364	0.02909	0.04795
18	0.02936	0.06364	0.02909	0.04795
20	0.02936	0.06364	0.02909	0.04795
22	0.02936	0.06364	0.02909	0.04795
24	0.02936	0.06364	0.02909	0.04795
26	0.02936	0.06364	0.02909	0.04795
28	0.02936	0.06364	0.02909	0.04795
30	0.02936	0.06364	0.02909	0.04795
37	0.0568	0.0044	0.05737	0.029
44	0.0568	0.0044	0.05737	0.029
51	0.0568	0.0044	0.05737	0.029
58	0.0568	0.0044	0.05737	0.029
65	0.0568	0.0044	0.05737	0.029
72	0.0568	0.0044	0.05737	0.029

79	0.0568	0.0044	0.05737	0.029
86	0.0568	0.0044	0.05737	0.029
93	0.0568	0.0044	0.05737	0.029
100	0.0568	0.0044	0.05737	0.029

London VAAC

See Osman et al., 2020 for details, Default is based on Mount Redoubt 1990, Fine is based on Eyjafjallajökull 2010 and Coarse is based on Hekla 1991.

Default	Diameter (μm)	Cumulative Fraction
	0.1	0.0
	0.3	0.001
	1.0	0.006
	3.0	0.056
	10.0	0.256
	30.0	0.956
	100.0	1.0
Fine	0.1	0.0
	2.0	0.0219
	3.9	0.1027
	7.8	0.2630
	15.6	0.4507
	31.2	0.6112
	62.5	0.8027
	125.0	1.0
Coarse	0.1	0.0
	5.5	0.008005822
	7.8	0.013828239
	11.0	0.029112082
	15.6	0.053857351
	2.1	0.08588064
	31.2	0.155021834
	44.2	0.276564774
	62.5	0.433770015
	88.3	0.64992722
	125.0	1.0

Montréal VAAC

Size Distribution	Bin	Phi	Diameter Range (μm)	Mass Fraction ¹ (%)	Cumulative Mass Fraction (%)
Spurr 18 August 1992	1	11	$0.5 < d \leq 1$	0.1	0.1
	2	10	$1 < d \leq 2$	0.2	0.3
	3	9	$2 < d \leq 4$	1.6	1.9
	4	8	$4 < d \leq 8$	2.5	4.4
	5	7	$8 < d \leq 16$	5.5	9.9
	6	6	$16 < d \leq 31$	8.0	17.9
	7	5	$31 < d \leq 62.5$	11.0	28.9
	8	4	$62.5 < d \leq 125$	11.5	40.4
	9	3	$125 < d \leq 250$	23.0	63.4
	10	2	$250 < d \leq 500$	6.0	69.4
	11	1	$500 < d \leq 1000$	4.0	73.4
	12	0	$1000 < d \leq 2000$	5.6	79.0
	13	-1	$2000 < d \leq 4000$	7.0	86.0
	14	-2	$4000 < d \leq 8000$	7.0	93.0
	15	-3	$8000 < d \leq 16000$	5.0	98.0
	16	-4	$16000 < d \leq 32000$	1.8	99.8
	17	-5	$32000 < d \leq 64000$	0.2	100.0
Spurr 16-17 September 1992	1	11	$0.5 < d \leq 1$	0.1	0.1
	2	10	$1 < d \leq 2$	0.3	0.4
	3	9	$2 < d \leq 4$	2.4	2.8
	4	8	$4 < d \leq 8$	3.8	6.6
	5	7	$8 < d \leq 16$	6.5	13.1
	6	6	$16 < d \leq 31$	10.2	23.3

	7	5	$31 < d \leq 62.5$	17.0	40.3
	8	4	$62.5 < d \leq 125$	23.5	63.8
	9	3	$125 < d \leq 250$	16.0	79.8
	10	2	$250 < d \leq 500$	2.0	81.8
	11	1	$500 < d \leq 1000$	2.5	84.3
	12	0	$1000 < d \leq 2000$	5.5	89.8
	13	-1	$2000 < d \leq 4000$	3.0	92.8
	14	-2	$4000 < d \leq 8000$	1.8	94.6
	15	-3	$8000 < d \leq 16000$	2.5	97.1
	16	-4	$16000 < d \leq 32000$	2.0	99.1
	17	-5	$32000 < d \leq 64000$	0.6	99.7
	18	-6	$64000 < d \leq 128000$	0.3	100.0
	2	9	$2 < d \leq 4$	25.0	50.0
	3	8	$4 < d \leq 8$	25.0	75.0
	4	7	$8 < d \leq 16$	25.0	100.0

Size Distribution	Bin	Phi	Diameter Range (μm)	Mass Fraction (%)	Cumulative Mass Fraction (%)
Redoubt 1989-1990 (empirical)	1		$0 < d \leq 2$	0.0	0.0
	2	9	$2 < d \leq 4$	2.5	2.5
	3	8	$4 < d \leq 8$	3.8	6.3
	4	7	$8 < d \leq 16$	5.6	11.9
	5	6	$16 < d \leq 32$	10.2	22.1
	6	5	$32 < d \leq 62$	14.3	36.4
	7	4	$62 < d \leq 125$	22.4	58.8
	8	3	$125 < d \leq 250$	19.3	78.1
	9	2	$250 < d \leq 500$	15.3	93.4

	10	1	$500 < d \leq 1000$	6.6	100.0
Default Size Distribution in NAME London VAAC, UK Met Office	1		$0.1 < d \leq 0.3$	0.1	0.1
	2		$0.3 < d \leq 1$	0.5	0.6
	3		$1 < d \leq 3$	5.0	5.6
	4		$3 < d \leq 10$	20.0	25.6
	5		$10 < d \leq 30$	70.0	95.6
	6		$30 < d \leq 100$	4.4	100.0
Fine	1		$0 < d \leq 2$	25.0	25.0
	2	9	$2 < d \leq 4$	25.0	50.0
	3	8	$4 < d \leq 8$	25.0	75.0
	4	7	$8 < d \leq 16$	25.0	100.0

Toulouse VAAC

Diameter (um)	Weight	Cumulative Fraction
0.2	0.001	0.001
0.65	0.005	0.006
2.0	0.05	0.056
6.5	0.2	0.256
20.0	0.7	0.956
65.0	0.044	1.0

Tokyo VAAC

For volcanic ash cloud (Suzuki, 1983). Values of diameter are set continuously for tracers in actual calculation.

Diameter (um)	Weight	Cumulative Fraction
1.0	0.0	0.0
1.25	0.072	0.072
2.0	0.192	0.264
4.0	0.357	0.621
8.0	0.307	0.928
10.0	0.072	1.0

Wellington VAAC

Diameter (um)	Weight	Cumulative Fraction
0.65	0.006	0.006
2.0	0.05	0.056
6.5	0.2	0.256
20.0	0.7	0.956
65.0	0.044	1.0

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